

TEACH AS YOU PREACH – ACTIVATING PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING FOR UNIVERSITY TEACHERS IN LAPPEENRANTA-LAHTI UNIVERSITY OF TECHNOLOGY

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ABSTRACT

Lappeenranta-Lahti University of Technology (LUT) offers its teaching staff various pedagogical training courses. This paper describes the first module, “University Pedagogy, Basic Module (10 ECTS), and its feedback and results. The module itself was compiled in collaboration between two universities: the ordering university LUT and the delivering university Tampere University of Applied Sciences (TAMK). In pedagogical training it is important to teach as you preach. The participants should be able to experience themselves all the methods, principles, and skills they are supposed to acquire during the training. It is difficult to learn to activate students or to become student-centred only by listening to lectures. Therefore, the teaching methods should be in line with the learning goals and the participants should be active doers and learn hands-on rather than be passive listeners. The Basic Module

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contents focused on two main aspects: general activating pedagogical skills and teacher's digital tools and their use from pedagogical point of view. First, the basic elements of the pedagogical module are presented together with its structure. Second, the results of participants' experienced learning gains in different categories of the contents are presented together with their perception of the importance of different parts of the content.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 Pedagogical training in LUT University

At LUT University teaching staff is not required to have pedagogical training - having a PhD in teacher's own field of research is the only strict requirement. However, pedagogical skills are valued and seen important by the university and therefore LUT offers the teaching staff the opportunity to take pedagogical training courses. The studies consist of one 10 ects basic module followed by optional optional other courses, e.g. "*Supervising Doctoral Studies*", "*Interaction and teaching presence*" and various other courses in co-operation with other Finnish universities. Teachers will receive a certificate of their teaching skills, and they can use that in their performance discussions within the department or use it otherwise in their life-long learning plan. The goal of the training is to develop and support LUT teaching and research staff's pedagogical and teaching skills, enhance interaction skills and strengthen teacher identity. The 10-credit basic module is bought from other organization (TAMK) and the optional courses are provided by LUT University.

1.2 Activating methods in teaching

Active learning covers a variety of instructional methods which engage students as active participants instead of (passive) listeners of lecturing. Active learning is usually defined as any instructional method that engages students in the learning process. Thus, engaging and activating students during their learning process are the core principles of active learning [1]. In science, technology, engineering and mathematics (abbreviation STEM), examples of active learning methods are i.e. simulations, demonstration, laboratory work calculating, group discussion, peer instruction, taking online exercises, self-assessment, quizzes, using clickers and polling to collect individual and group opinions and explanations and so on. Such instructional methods promote students' own activity and taking responsibility of their own learning process. Instead of passively listening to a lecturing, students actively do learning activities and process information in various ways. They also need to present their ideas and conceptions to their peers in discussions. Different studies have highlighted benefits of active-engagement learning methods. Prince [1] has found support for all forms of active learning examined in his studies. Freeman et al. [2] carried out a meta-analysis of 225 studies that had reported course scores and passing rates in STEM courses, and they compared results of studies between traditional lecturing method and active learning methods. Their analysis indicated that using active learning methods can increase passing rates and course scores. Deslauriers et al. [3] has shown improved learning outcomes in a large-enrolment

physics class when using pre-class reading assignments, pre-class reading quizzes, in-class clicker questions with student-student discussion, small-group active learning tasks and targeted in-class instructor feedback. Especially, they found that active learning methods have great benefits with small groups, but it is effective for all group sizes. Wieman has found similar positive effects [4]. In addition to active-engagement methods, also self-regulatory skills are also often connected with active learning. Research has shown that when mastering own learning process, learning outcomes are typically better [5, 6].

2 ARRANGEMENTS AND CONTENTS OF THE PEDAGOGICAL TRAINING

2.1 Participants

The module was offered to teaching staff of LUT University. From the applicants, 22 were chosen based on the urgency of the need for the training and on their ability to commit to the working on the module. Despite the commitment requirement, the number of participants dropped a little after the beginning and 20 participants continued to the end of the first semester. When the semester changed, 17 participants continued studying on the module. Figure 1 presents the overall activity on the module, based on the weekly sum of log events in Moodle, together with the number of active participants. The activity is found to be strongly correlated with the assignment deadlines and contact days, which are show later in Fig. 2.

Fig. 1. Weekly sum of Moodle log events (left axis) and the number of active participants (right axis) as a function of course week.

2.2 The module: “University Pedagogy, Basic Module (10 ECTS)”

The first part of the pedagogical training was arranged as a 10 ects module, called “University Pedagogy, Basic Module”. Teaching consisted of three contact days, three online afternoons and online guidance sessions. Studying was mostly done online in groups and individually between the contact days and online sessions. For clarity, the materials were divided in three parts and collected under the following titles: “Building pedagogical skills in modern learning environment”, “Digital tools for

effective teaching”, and “Development work”. All these three themes formed an intertwined and coherent entity, and they couldn’t be accomplished separately. Instead, participants were expected to accomplish the whole study module of 10 ects as a whole. To help the participants to keep on track and to meet the deadlines, all assignments were shown as a timeline list in the beginning of the Moodle contents. The lines of the list were links to the corresponding material, assignments or site in the Moodle. A screenshot of the timeline is shown in Figure 2.

Module Timeline & deadlines

This table contains contact and online days, together with deadlines for assignments. Contact days are from 9:00 to 16:00. Online hours are 13:00-16:00. The categories refer to different courses of the module as follows:

- Building pedagogical skills in modern learning environment
- Digital tools for effective teaching
- Development work

The texts in "Name" column work as links to corresponding materials and assignments

Name	Deadline	Category	Indiv./Group
Preliminary assignments (assignments 1-4)	10.10.2021		
Contact Day 1 (12.10.2021 9:00-16:00) Room 2305, LUT Lappeenranta			
Online Afternoon 1 (20.10.2021 13:00-16:00)			
Learning theories (assignment 5)	7.11.2021		
Contact Day 2 (9.11.2021 9:00-16:00) Room: Rantasauna			
Development work plan (assignment 6)	30.11.2021		
Comment others' development plans (assignment 7)	7.12.2021		
Curriculum, description, production (assignment 8)	13.12.2021		
Produce your own teaching video clip (assignment 9)	11.1.2022		
Comment other's video clips (assignment 10)	17.1.2022		
Teams and Zoom skills (assignment 11)	17.1.2022		
Online Afternoon 2 (19.1.2022 13:00-16:00)			
Poll+Video: Pre- and misconceptions (assignment 12)	13.2.2022		
Assessment (assignment 13)	20.2.2022		
Online Afternoon 3 (23.2.2022 13:00-16:00)			
Mid-work check: development work draft (assignment 14)	20.3.2022		
Reserve development work meeting (assignment 15)	20.3.2022		
Hand in your development work (doc + PP) (assignment 16)	21.4.2022		
FINAL SEMINAR (28.4.2022 11:30-15:30)			

Fig. 2. Moodle timeline, assignments and deadlines.

The learning objectives were described as skills – after completing the module the participants are able to: 1) Use an interactive and instructive working method, 2) Build courses and material in pedagogically meaningful way, 3) Select suitable pedagogical methods, 4) Select suitable education technology for the students

depending on the situation and learning environment and Justify the choice of this technology, and 5) Assess learning and competencies in varying ways.

The topics covered were (at the title level):

- Learning Theories
- Activating teaching methods
- Curriculum development
- Different aspects of assessment
- Video tools
- Polling as an activating method
- Learning analytics,
- Pre- and misconceptions,
- Learning management systems
- Own teaching videos.

The idea of the “Development work” was to take the learned skills and the acquired knowledge into use immediately. The participants were asked to choose one of the courses they are currently teaching or will be teaching in the near future. They needed to make a plan how to improve the course contents, arrangements, teaching methods etc. according to their own needs. First, they were asked to describe the current status and define the needs for improvements concerning the course. Second, they needed to describe the pedagogical background behind their decisions for improvements. And finally present their solutions for tackling the challenges they had on their course setup.

2.3 Teach as you preach

“Teach as you preach” means that you use the same activating methods with your students (participants) in practice what you expect them to use later in their teaching career. Rather than lecturing or delivering information about engaging and activating teaching practices through traditional approaches, the very same methods are in use on the course and thus the participants can have own experience of the methods from students’ point of view. When starting a new topic, the facilitators first gave a brief introduction. This was accompanied by polling the prior understanding of the topic. Anonymous polling was used to create a safe learning environment in which every participant felt safe to bring her/his opinion to the discussion. When contradicting points of view emerged, group discussions were initiated to widen the perspectives of all participants, including that of the facilitators. Many of the assignments included group working, discussions in small groups, self- and peer evaluation of the participants outputs etc. For example, when dealing with different learning theories, the participants were first asked to study individually, then collect a summary of the characteristic features of different theories in small groups. After this they were asked to evaluate different parts of the ongoing course “University Pedagogy, Basic Module” and the actions of the facilitators from learning theories perspective. Which parts of the teaching were based on socio-cultural learning theory? How can you tell? Which actions and assignments had characteristics of connectivism? How can you tell? etc. Similarly, when discussing about how to build a clear and pedagogically planned Moodle site, the participants were given an evaluation rubric and asked to use it to evaluate the very course “University

Pedagogy, Basic Module”. This was then again followed by a discussion of the findings and different points of view. Since the participants came from engineering departments, many of the activating demonstrations and examples were picked also from engineering education.

3 RESULTS

3.1 Feedback survey

Microsoft Forms was used to collect the feedback about the module and participants’ personal perception of their own learning of the topics. Most of the questions were presented on 7-point Likert scale accompanied with optional free text field. The number of questions was purposely kept low and thus the average answering time was 13 minutes. The answer rate was 65 %, calculated from the active participants at the end of the study module.

3.2 Learning gains

The perceived learning gain was measured by asking the participants two questions about the course contents and topics: 1) “How much do you feel that you know about the following topics/skills at the moment?” 2) “How much do you feel that you knew about the following topics/skills at before this 10 ects basic module?”

The answer distribution to the first question is presented in Fig. 3. Most of the participants seem to consider their current knowledge of the topics to be way above neutral (4), some even at the level of expert.

Fig. 3. Answer distributions to question “How much do you feel that you know about the following topics/skills at the moment?”. 1= Nothing, 7=Expert.

The perceived knowledge before the module is presented in Fig. 4. Not many of the participants were familiar with the course topics and many of the answers are either 1 or 2 (nothing or almost nothing). Thus, the study module served its purpose and the participants feel that they have learned a lot. This perceived learning gain is presented in Fig. 5. It is calculated by taking the averages of answers to different

topics from figures 3 and 4. The beginning of the arrow represents the answer average before this study module and the end represents the average after it. Thus, the length of the arrow shows the average perceived gain in a certain topic.

Fig. 4. Answer distributions to question “How much do you feel that you know about the following topics/skills before this 10 ects basic module?”. 1= Nothing, 7=Expert.

Fig. 5. Perceived learning gains on different topics of the study module.

In many of the topics the gains were remarkably high: polling (2.8), learning theories (2.7) and misconceptions (2.7). On the other hand, video conferencing tools and producing own educational videos were already familiar to the participants, probably due to the Covid-19 pandemic, and thus the gains were the smallest.

3.3 Importance of the module topics

The participants were asked to evaluate the importance of the different topics covered in the training in a scale 1 (not important at all) to 7 (very important). The answer distributions and averages are shown in Fig. 6. The two most important

topics were Moodle and production of own educational videos. These choices are quite natural, since Moodle is used to deliver courses, teaching contents and assignments and videos are one main content delivery method. In these topics the learning gains (Fig. 5) were not the highest, but at the same time the levels were high. This tells that these topics are considered very relevant and necessary even though the participants were already rather skilled in them before the training module. The two topics that the participants were the least familiar with were learning theories and student misconceptions. The latter gained also rather high score in the importance rating (6.0) and its learning gain was among the top three (2.7). Thus, it seems that the participants realized how much of a barrier misconceptions form to learning - an essential point of view in constructivistic learning theory.

Fig. 6. Participant answer distributions and averages importance of the different topics covered in the pedagogical training.

4 SUMMARY AND CONCLUSIONS

We have briefly shown what kind of elements the pedagogical training had, what kind of topics were covered and how the “teach as you preach” principle was applied in facilitating the course. The participants’ experienced learning gains were found to be rather high and the participants found the topics relevant for their teaching career. It would be interesting and informative to interview the participants after a couple of years of teaching career: how would they then see the course and the skills it provided? What impact the pedagogical training had on their teaching career? Etc. Unfortunately, these questions can be answered only in the future.

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